

Nuclear Deterrence and European Peace

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ABSTRACT

This paper traces the causality behind the peace⁶ in Europe from 1945 to 1991. It argues that there were three major reasons behind it. 1) Peace in Europe from 1945 to 1991 held because of the extended nuclear deterrence between the US and the USSR. 2) Western European countries did not fight among themselves because they were scared that the USSR would immediately take advantage of their fight and would not hesitate in intervening. 3) The countries of Eastern Europe did not fight among themselves because the USSR had clearly warned them that they had only limited sovereignty and their foreign policies could not go against the wishes of Moscow. This paper also analyzes why the European Peace held even after the Soviet Union dissolved.

This paper is divided into four parts. The first part compares post World War 2 Europe with the earlier period and argues that Europe after 1945 has been remarkably more peaceful than at earlier times. The second part argues that European Peace had less to do with Europe and more to do with the nuclear deterrence equation established between American and Soviet blocks. The third part posits that Western European countries did not fight with each other because of the threat from the Soviet Union, and the Eastern European countries could not fight with each other because they were under the strict control of Soviet Union. The fourth part explores the reasons behind European peace after the disintegration of the Soviet Union.

European Peace

There is no doubt that Europe has been the site of some of the most devastating wars in human history. The Treaty of Westphalia (which actually was a series of treaties signed between May and October 1648) ended the Thirty Years war and the Eighty Years war and established the modern state system of Europe. However this European state system was prone to wars since its very beginning. Mearshiemer (1990) correctly notes:

The European state system has been plagued with war since its inception. During much of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries war was underway somewhere on the European continent. The nineteenth century held longer periods of peace, but also several major wars and crises. The first half of that century witnessed the protracted and bloody Napoleonic Wars; later came the Crimean War, and the Italian and German wars of unification. The wars of 1914-1945 continued this long historical pattern. They

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represented a break from the events of previous centuries only in the enormous increase in their scale of destruction.

Geeraerts and Stouthusen (1999) point out that from a historical perspective Europe has been the most belligerent region of the world. In 25 out of the 75 interstate wars between 1815 and 1993, the war action took place at least partly in Europe. Moreover, in 31 wars one or more European countries participated on both sides, while in 46 wars at least one European country took part. Of the 31 million battle casualties in all interstate wars since 1815, 31 wars among European countries accounted for 25 million deaths or 80 percent of the casualties. Finally, Europe was the starting point of the two world wars, which are the most devastating wars in the history of humanity.

Mearsheimer (1990) writes that the years from 1945 to 1991 represent the longest period of peace in Europe. During these years Europe saw no major wars, and only two minor conflicts (the 1956 Soviet intervention in Hungary and the 1974 Greco-Turkish war in Cyprus). Neither conflict threatened to spread to other countries. The early years of Cold War (1945-1963) were marked by a handful of major crises, although none brought Europe to the brink of war. The peace in the years of the Cold War is in sharp contrast with the earlier centuries and especially with the first 45 years of the 20th century. The first 45 years of the 20th century witnessed two world wars, a handful of minor wars, and a number of crises that almost resulted in war. Some 50 million Europeans were killed in the two world wars; in contrast, probably no more than 15,000 died in the two post-1945 European conflicts. The Cold War years in Europe were decidedly more peaceful than the early part of the 20th century.

Geeraerts and Stouthuysen (1999) also concur with this view. They write that since 1945 Europe has been comparatively more peaceful. Between 1945 and 1989 the Correlates of War Project notifies only three wars in Europe. Interestingly, they have long time-intervals between them and decrease in size. Although an increase in overall violence in Europe occurred immediately after the end of the Cold War, the number of violent conflicts is again very low.

John Lewis Gaddis in 1989 coined the term 'the long peace' to describe the unprecedented decades of peace in post-World War 2 Europe. At the end of the Cold War many scholars wondered whether Europe's peace was going to hold or the continent would descend into chaos yet again. Articles such as "Why We will Soon Miss the Cold War" were written in order to establish a causal relationship between the Cold War and the long peace of Europe. But, interestingly, contrary to most guesstimates, the peace in Europe held. Of course, there were a handful of small wars in the Balkans during the 1990s, but the major European powers did not start them, did not exploit them for national gain, and with the help of the United States ultimately managed to bring them to an end. Very importantly, there has been no war between any of the major powers. Indeed, there has been a little security competition among them (Mearsheimer 2010).

Tracing Causality

This section argues that the equation of the nuclear deterrence established between America and the Soviet Union was the root cause of the long peace. The reason that Western European countries did not fight among themselves was that they were stuck between two hegemonies: America and the Soviet Union. One they feared and united against, the other protected them and offered security with the implicit condition that they will not fight among themselves because the Soviet Union would not miss any pretext for intervention in West Europe. Eastern European countries did not fight among themselves because of the Brezhnev Doctrine that stated that they have only limited sovereignty and this sovereignty did not extend to the level of fighting wars with each other, which would have been contrary to the interests of the Soviet Union. The peace after the end of the Cold War and the disintegration of the Soviet Union can be attributed to the Democratic Peace theory, which states that democracies do not fight wars with each other, and to the pacifying effects of free trade, championed by the European Union.

Nuclear Deterrence

There can be no ironclad theories in social sciences. Yet it is important to theorize and apply those theories to real life situations. Only then it can be seen whether this seemingly senseless world makes some kind of sense and whether lessons learnt from one situation can be applied to another situation. In academic parlance, it is referred to as the Nomothetic Approach. It is contrasted with the Idiographic Approach, which assumes that every situation is unique and generalizations cannot be made. This paper utilizes the Nomothetic Approach and I believe that theories should be applied to real life situations, as this is a way to test the robustness of theories.

Yes, there can be no ironclad theories in social sciences including International Relations. But two theories come as close as possible to ironclad laws. One is the Nuclear Deterrence theory and the other is the Democratic Peace theory. While the former is used to explain the long peace in Europe during the Cold War, the latter can be utilized to explain the post-Soviet Union peace in Europe.

Nuclear Deterrence basically means that two nuclear-armed countries or group do not fight wars with each other. If country A and Country B have nuclear weapons and have assured second strike capabilities then both will be deterred from attacking each other. Assured second strike capability means that a country has the capacity of absorbing a first nuclear strike and still be capable of guaranteeing its attacker that it will be left with enough nuclear weapons to inflict unacceptable damage to the attacker. If A and B both have this capability, then they will not attack each other, because both realize that any initiation may lead the dyad climbing the escalation ladder and this could result in the complete destruction of both A and B. It does not mean that there will be friendship between the two countries. It simply means both A and B realize that it is not worth getting destroyed oneself in order to destroy the other. Getting oneself destroyed is too big a price to pay and it is an irrational choice to initiate war with a nuclear-armed rival. Sridharan (2007) captures the essence of nuclear deterrence by writing:

In a dyadic nuclear relationship the core of nuclear deterrence theory is that a state will be deterred from launching a nuclear attack against another state, or a major conventional attack that carries the risk of escalation to the nuclear level, if it has good reasons to fear retaliation. Deterrence theory assumes the centrality of survival as a core value. This is subsumed in the assumption of rationality, i.e., states will not want to suffer the risk of extinction or the enormous devastation that is inevitable in absorbing nuclear strikes. Assumption of a rational, cost-benefit calculating, risk-assessing behavior by decision-makers and a survivable second-strike capacity on the part of a state vis-à-vis its antagonist are the bases of nuclear deterrence.

The US entered into the NATO pact with West European countries and in response the Soviet Union and East European countries established the Warsaw pact. The conditions of the NATO and the Warsaw Pact were almost identical. America promised its West European allies that if they were attacked, America will respond with full might as if its own homeland had been attacked. The Soviet Union also extended the security umbrella to its East European allies. NATO deployed nuclear weapons in West Europe and the Soviet Union did the same in East Europe (Borger 2012).¹ When a state provides nuclear security umbrella to other state or states, it is called extended nuclear deterrence. Anderson and Larsen (2013, 4) write, "using generic terms, extended deterrence can be described as Blue deterring adversary Red from taking actions to intimidate, coerce, or attack third-party Green. While the desired outcome of extended deterrence is the preservation and protection of Green, the focus and object of extended deterrence as a strategic concept is Red. Green may be passive, indifferent, or even unaware of the actions of Blue. For Blue, extended deterrence is centered on the following question: What deters Red from coercing, threatening, or attacking Green." Both America and the Soviet Union adopted the postures of extended deterrence, thus a cold war engulfed Europe. Both America and the Soviet Union had developed assured second strike capability by deploying a nuclear triad which means that in order to enhance its second strike capability a country deploys nuclear weapons on the ground, in the air by fighter jets and in the water by using submarines. The whole idea is to let the enemy know that he can never be certain that he can destroy all your nuclear weapons. It is this uncertainty that deters. According to nuclear doctrines of both countries if the operators of the nuclear weapons were to know that their homeland had been attacked, they were supposed to go ahead with nuclear attack on pre-decided targets. It was to be assumed that their leadership has been decapitated and is not in a position to order attacks. America toyed with the ideas of massive retaliation and gradual response. The Massive

¹Due to Iron Curtain, it is difficult to quantify how many nuclear weapons were deployed by Soviet Union in East European theater. Luczak (1996, 19), for example, notes in the case of Poland that the country never possessed nuclear weapons of its own. After the World War 2, Soviet Union maintained a large troops presence in Poland and these troops did have nuclear weapons.

retaliation doctrine says that if a country has been attacked with nuclear weapons, its response will not be in proportion to the attack. It will make a massive retaliation to inflict unacceptable damage to the attacker. Gradual response says that if a country has been attacked with nuclear weapons, it will respond with a proportional attack or may be with a little more than proportion. The idea was that if the USSR were to target a European country and America were to respond with massive retaliation to inflict unacceptable damage, then the USSR would have no option but to use its nuclear arsenal to destroy America completely. Logically, it was not worth getting destroyed oneself for avenging the loss of a European city. Thus later on America gravitated more towards the gradual response. But this did not affect the deterrence equation adversely. On the contrary it made the deterrence equation more credible and rational and enhanced mutual fear. Both America and the Soviet Union realized that any fight between them over a European city would result in nuclear catastrophe. This resulted in both blocks being satisfied with their share of Europe and the long peace prevailed in the continent. They could and they did fight proxy wars in the third world but Europe was left more or less untouched.² Next part analyzes why Western And Eastern European countries did not fight among themselves.

A-West Europe: Stuck between Two Hegemons

Now we come to the question of why the countries of Western Europe did not fight among themselves. Morgenthau argued that an international system is anarchic since there is no universal hegemon to enforce rules, norms and morality. This makes the international system a self-help system in which states are aware that their security is their own responsibility. The search for security makes states power-maximizing entities. There are only two ways of increasing power: internal balancing and external balancing. When states increase their power by utilizing internal resources, it is referred to as internal balancing, while external balancing involves forming alliances with other states. Having said that, Europe was fortunate that there were two hegemons that did not let anarchy take over the continent and Morgenthau's principles, although extremely popular in international relations theory, never really applied in post World War 2 Europe. America enforced rules and norms in West Europe while Soviet Union did the same in East Europe. This gives us a clue, why West European states did not fight with one another during the long peace even when they had a history of centuries of warfare behind them. Suppose there are two hegemons in a system, A and B. There are C, D, E and F countries also in the system. A is perceived as a benign hegemon offering them

²This has been explained as a stability/instability paradox. According to Jervis (1984, 31), at macro level, nuclear weapons create stability but at micro level states are emboldened to take advantages because they are sure that their enemy will hesitate in taking strong action, since any provocative move could result in escalation of the conflict and may eventually reach nuclear level.

security via an alliance. B is seen as a malign hegemon and perceived as a threat. In such a scenario push and pull factors are automatically created for C, D, E and F. They are naturally inclined towards hegemon A because there are two reasons forcing them to do it. One is the fear of B, which is a push factor and another is the attraction of A which becomes a pull factor because of the protection offered. This is precisely what happened with the countries of Western Europe. They were terribly afraid of the Soviet Union and their fear was genuine. They were offered protection and massive aid for economic reconstruction by America via NATO alliance. But America would not tolerate any infighting among Western European countries. First of all, it would weaken the alliance and second it could provoke the Soviet Union to take advantage of the situation by intervening. The Soviet Union was always ready for that and would not have missed an opportunity. This forced Western European countries to remain united and loyal to America. So, it was fear mixed with the instinct for self-protection that forced Western European countries to stay at peace with each other. They were stuck between two hegemonies. Naturally, they chose the side of the hegemon which they perceived as benign. The conditions enforced by the benign hegemon and the threat from the malign hegemon compelled them to remain at peace with each other.

East Europe: The Compulsions of Brezhnev Doctrine

It is not difficult to understand why East European countries did not fight with each other. They too were stuck between two hegemonies. For them the Soviet Union was the benign one. The same push and pull factors were operating in the Eastern block also. But apart from this, there was one more important cause behind peace in Eastern Europe. The Brezhnev Doctrine clearly stated that the countries of East Europe only have limited sovereignty. These countries did not even have full internal sovereignty. It was impossible for them even to think about entering into a war within the block, which would jeopardize the cohesion of the Warsaw Pact. The Soviet Union always made it very clear that no country from Eastern Europe would be allowed to jeopardize the cohesion of the Communist block. The Soviet Union invaded Hungary in 1956 to curb the demand for democracy and openness. In similar fashion it invaded Czechoslovakia in 1968 to put an end to the Prague Spring. Kovalev (1968) elucidated the Brezhnev Doctrine in a Pravda article, titled "Sovereignty and the International Obligations of Socialist Countries." While addressing the Polish United Workers' Party on November 13, 1968, Brezhnev said that when capitalist forces try to intervene in the domestic politics of any Socialist country, then it is not only the problem of that particular country but a challenge to all socialist countries (Gross 1990). Popa (1972), a staunch critic of Soviet interventionist policies, defined the Brezhnev doctrine succinctly:

According to the Brezhnevian concepts of "limited sovereignty" the countries of the so-called "socialist community" do not enjoy the right to determine their foreign policy freely and in a sovereign way, but are compelled to obtain the approval of the Soviet social-imperialists in everything. These countries have no right to strive for a foreign policy independent of the Soviet Union and to establish diplomatic and economic relations with other countries without its consent. The aim of the Soviet social-imperialists is thus the transformation of the foreign policies of the other revisionist

countries into an obedient appendage of the circumstances and zigzags of Soviet foreign policy.....According to the social-imperialist concepts of "limited sovereignty" which the Soviet ruling clique is preaching, the revisionists member countries of the infamous Warsaw Treaty do not enjoy even the right to sovereign disposition over their national territories, while the Soviet militarists have the right, under the pretext of military maneuvers in the framework of the Warsaw treaty, to enter and leave these countries with their armed forces as in their own land.

It is obvious that the countries of Eastern Europe did not fight among themselves because they simply could not. The Soviet Union exerted too much pressure to make it impossible for them to settle scores by fighting with each other. The national interests of East European countries were subjugated to the larger interest of the communist block as defined by Soviet Union.

Europe in Post 1991 Era

Although this paper basically confines itself to the timeframe of 1945 to 1991, but it is difficult to conclude this paper without mentioning that Europe has remained peaceful even after 1991. Apart from the breakup of Yugoslavia and the violence attendant to it, Europe from 1991 till date has remained almost as peaceful as in the post World War 2 decades. Scholars like Mearsheimer predicted around the time of the breakup of the Soviet Union that forthcoming decades in Europe were going to be not so peaceful (Mearsheimer 1990, 5). He also wrote a provocatively titled paper, "Why We will Soon Miss the Cold War" (Mearsheimer 1990). But his dire predictions never came true. Mearsheimer (2010) himself was the first to acknowledge this. Actually nobody had imagined that Europe was going to be as peaceful in post-Soviet Union era as it has been. It is hardly a surprise that the European Union won the Nobel Prize for peace. But tracing the causal chain behind Europe's post-cold war peace is not difficult. First and foremost credit goes to a factor which again lies outside Europe. With the dissolution of the Warsaw Pact, America had an attractive option of dissolving NATO and getting out of Europe. But America maintained its commitment to Europe and further expanded NATO (Risse and Walter-Drop, 2009). Thus America remained a hegemon in Europe, which according to the realist paradigm of the International Relations theory stopped Europe going the anarchical way. America maintained itself in the position of imposing rules and norms and did not allow any country to play rogue.

NATO has several important post-Cold War roles. These roles include providing a hedge against long term revival of Russian expansionism, projecting stability eastward by taking in new members as well as by contributing to the establishment of cooperative European security system, and helping to prevent the reemergence of national rivalries in Europe. However, the later two roles are largely non-military in nature.

This is the reason that no country tried to take advantage of the breakup of Yugoslavia, and violence could ultimately be contained with the emergence of six independent countries.

For understanding the other factors behind the post-Cold War European peace, there is a need to utilize the liberal paradigm of the International Relations theory. The literature

of International Relations is flooded with paradigm wars between realism and liberalism, but there is a need to understand that in spite of being contradictory to each other both theories have tremendous explanatory power and it is futile to select one and discard the other. The important thing is to realize which theory is important in a particular situation. Immanuel Kant is considered to be the father of the liberal theory of International Relations. He gave the three-legged theory of international peace (Russett, O'Neal and Davis 1998, 441). He said free trade, democratic governments and influential inter-governmental organizations will be the vanguard of international peace. This is exactly what happened in post-Cold War Europe. The European Union kept on expanding and took more and more countries in its fold. The free trade led by the European Union kept the process of European integration going at an amazing speed. Fortunately, countries of East Europe and most members of the Confederation of Independent States (CIS) became democracies and democratic peace became a norm in Europe. Yes, there were differences about the war in Iraq and how to handle Iran's nuclear program among other issues, but none of

the problems were so severe that they could break European unity or Europe's strong alliance with America. Even now Europe is passing through an unprecedented era of economic crisis and there are differences among EU countries about how to handle it, but so far the issue has not threatened the strength of European peace.

Conclusion

This paper has argued that the equation of extended nuclear deterrence between America and the Soviet Union, the fear of the Soviet Union among Western European countries and limited sovereignty of the Eastern European countries maintained peace in post World War 2 Europe. After the disintegration of the Soviet Union, it was the continued commitment of America, the expanding influence of European Union, free trade and acceleration of the European integration process and the adoption of democracy by the newly independent countries which became key variables in maintaining peace in Europe

Limitations of the Paper

This paper could be strongly criticized on the grounds that it makes sweeping generalizations, uses facts selectively to put forward arguments favored by the author and contributes nothing new. The purpose of this paper has been to trace dominant factors behind European peace. Thus some amount of generalization was necessary. Facts may have been selectively used but none of the facts challenging the arguments put forward in this paper have been ignored. The stress in this paper has not been on novelty but on the application of the theories of International Relations to understand the phenomenon of European peace.

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